

Microbial Loads in Faeces of Weaner Rabbits (*Oryctolagus Cuniculus*) Fed Bioslurry Diet

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Abstract

Faecal microbial analysis is a powerful tool for assessing the health and performance of weaner rabbits. This study examines the intricate relationship between diet and faecal microbiota composition in weaner rabbits, and investigates the feasibility of incorporating biogas slurry into animal feed without adversely affecting the microbial gut content. The primary objective was to determine the effect of feeding diets containing graded levels of biogas slurry on the faecal micro-biodata and Coliform content. Twenty-four 6-week-old rabbits were used, nursed for 2 weeks, and then distributed into 3 weight-similar groups. Each group received one of three diets containing 0%, 5%, or 10% sun-dried biogas slurry, a nutrient-rich feed ingredient derived from the anaerobic degradation of chicken faeces. Rabbits were housed individually in cages in a completely randomized design. Feed intake and faecal samples were collected, and data were analyzed using ANOVA with SPSS Software (2016). The study found that rabbit groups fed diets with 5% and 10% biogas slurry showed no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in coliform content compared to control. This indicates that incorporating dried poultry droppings up to 10% in rabbit diets does not adversely affect the gut microflora of weaner rabbits, suggesting that biogas slurry, derived from poultry litter, can be a valuable dietary component for weaner rabbits. This could therefore offer an affordable and sustainable alternative feed, without compromising gut microbiota health. This research contributes to our understanding of dietary interventions in rabbit nutrition and sustainable livestock practices.

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1. Introduction

Rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) can be classified as micro livestock and has been increasingly reared in different parts of the world. They have a short generational interval with a gestation period of 28 - 31 days and could kindle up to ten kits. It is important that the microbial content of the gut be studied for various reasons which include but are not limited to the health of the rabbits; environmental pollution, especially of water by contaminated faeces; and the health of the farmer.

After emission of gas, semisolid poultry or cow dung derived from an outlet is called biogas slurry or bio-slurry (Rahman et. al, 2011). It has been known for a long time to be a manure material. Compared to composted manure and farmyard manure, bio-slurry from biogas has a significant amount of both macro- and micronutrients as well as readily available plant nutrients (Ishikawa et. al, 2006).

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These excreted nutrients can be recycled, thus making the bio-slurry a potentially useful nutritional source for animals. Bioslurry differs biochemically from the original raw material because it contains bioactive chemicals introduced during the digestion process. Bioslurry thus has a substantially higher nutrient availability than other undigested sources (Makadi, 2012). Essential elements like potassium, zinc, iron, manganese, and copper are among those found in the digested biogas slurry (Kumar et. al, 2015). Nutritional value in biogas slurry has been reported to range from 10% to more than 70%, depending on the type of dung and other feedstock, water, animals, type of digester, and anaerobic process used in biogas production (Ataei et. al, 2020).

Weaner rabbits are particularly vulnerable to dietary changes due to their developing gastrointestinal tract and rapidly evolving gut microbiota. The faecal microbiota, a dynamic consortium of microorganisms residing in the gastrointestinal tract, plays a crucial role in nutrient metabolism, immune modulation, and disease resistance. This study focuses on faecal microbial analysis as a window into the health and performance of weaner rabbits. Feed and feed additives such as probiotics influence the microbiome in an animal's gut. Biogas slurry is readily available and affordable, and therefore has the potential to be a valuable feed ingredient in rabbit diets in Nigeria. This study aims to investigate the feasibility of incorporating biogas slurry into animal feed without adversely affecting the microbial gut content.

Studies by Raj et al, 2011 show that biological treatments are the most obvious choice for handling this type of waste, and these technologies can maximize waste component recycling. It is crucial to recycle and use organic wastes and bi-products through the creation of a technology that is affordable, widely accepted by society, and ecologically beneficial because the widespread build-up of this waste generates pollution and poses disposal issues.

This study seeks to determine the effect of feeding diets containing graded levels of biogas slurry on the faecal microbiodata and Coliform content.

2. Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out at the rabbit unit of the Teaching and Research Farm, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. The experiment lasted for ten (10) weeks.

Experimental Animals

Twenty-four rabbits were used for this work and were purchased at 6 weeks of age, and nursed further for another 2 weeks on a common diet. This also served as a good adjustment period for the rabbits. To commence the trial, the rabbits were weighed individually and distributed into 3 groups of similar initial weight. Each group was allotted one of the treatment diets. Rabbits were housed individually in cages in complete randomization.

The biogas slurry used for this experiment was collected from As-Sabireen Lodge termed 'As-Sabireen Lodge Backyard Agricultural Value Chain' on a 60ft x 100 ft piece of zero waste, eco-friendly farming practice. The wet faeces voided by the caged chickens were loaded into a biodigester where anaerobic degradation of the materials occurs. This enables production of biogas, that is channeled directly to the kitchen for domestic cooking, and the biogas slurry waste which after sun-drying was incorporated directly into rabbit feed.

Preparation of the Experimental Diet

Three experimental diets were formulated by varying the proportions of feed ingredients. Diet T1 was the control diet (0 % BS), while diets T2 and T3 contained 5%, and 10 % Biogas Slurry (BS), respectively. Proximate analysis was carried out to determine the dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), crude fibre (CF), ether extract (EE) and ash components of the test material "biogas slurry" and the experimental diets using A.O.A.C (2005) method. The ingredients were weighed and manually mixed with hand and shovel for about five minutes to ensure thorough incorporation. The experimental diet was compounded as shown in Tables 1a -c.

The Experimental Design used is the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with 3 weaner rabbits allocated

randomly to three feeding regimens. The model for the response is:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \varphi_i + \epsilon_{ij}$$

Where, Y_{ij} = is the j-th response for the i-th treatment
 μ = constant component, common to all observations
 φ_i = i-th treatment effect
 ϵ_{ij} = experimental error

Data Collection

The Faecal samples were collected on the fifth and tenth weeks of the experiment. A net which was initially sterilized by cleaning with cotton wool soaked in Methylated Spirit was placed underneath the cages of the test animals and within the same hour, 1g of the droppings was collected using a different cotton swab for each animal and placed into a sterile tube.

Data Analysis

The data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and summarized using Standard Deviation and Mean. This was done using SPSS Software (2016).

Experimental Study

There were three treatments with an average of three rabbits in each treatment except the control where they were four. Each treatment group of rabbits was subjected to one of the three experimental diets which contained 0%, 5% and 10% biogas slurry respectively for the ten weeks of the experiment. Each rabbit was supplied 60g of feed and clean water each day and was increased to up to 70g in subsequent weeks based on their feed intake. Daily feed consumption was measured for each rabbit. Precautions were taken to minimize feed spillage..

3. Results and Discussion

Proximate Analysis of Feed Ingredients

Proximate composition of diets as shown in Table 1 were determined as follows: dry matter after drying at 105°C for 24h, Fat by petroleum ether extraction (Soxtherm, Gerhardt, Germany), protein content ($N \times 6.25$) by the Kjeldahl method after acid digestion, Ash by combustion at 550°C in a muffle furnace to a constant weight and crude fiber by acid/alkali digestion (AOAC, 1990).

Coliform Count of Rabbit Feces

Large-scale studies show that the cultivable fraction of rabbit digestive microbiota in healthy adults is characterized by the absence or low density of *Escherichia coli* (Yu and Tsen 1993; Pupoet al. 1997). Fortun-Lamothe and Boullier (2004) also made similar observations that *Escherichia coli* reached a maximum level at the 2nd or 3rd week of life and then decreased to be residual or absent after weaning in the gut of rabbits. A study by BogoneVantuset al. (2014) reported that microbes present in the gastrointestinal tract are a direct function of the nutrition of the rabbits. Combes et al. (2013) asserted that an abundant bacterial community is present throughout the caecum-colon and in the hard and soft faeces (1010 – 1012 bacteria/bag) of rabbits.

The results obtained for rabbit performance in terms of coliform content is presented in Table 2. Rabbit groups fed on the diet contained 5, 10% biogas slurry showed no ($P > 0.05$) significant difference in Coliform content. It was also found that *Escherichia Coli* formed the most part of the Coliform content.

Table 1a: Proximate Composition of Biogas Slurry (%)

Biogas Slurry	Percentage Composition
Moisture content	22.11
Ash content	44.41
Crude fibre	1.16
Ether Extract	3.73
Crude protein	14.88
NFE	12.7

¹NFE - Nitrogen free extract

Table 1b. Nutrient composition of experimental diets

INGREDIENTS (%)	TREATMENTS		
	T1(%)	T2 (%)	T3 (%)
Lysine	0.10	0.10	0.10
Salt	0.10	0.10	0.10
Limestone	0.40	0.20	0.20
Methionine	0.10	0.10	0.10
Premix	0.10	0.11	0.17
Palm kernel cake	35.00	33.09	31.09
Maize	27.56	29.38	26.38
Groundnut cake	18.04	15.68	14.68
Wheat offal	17.00	14.18	13.18
Palm oil	0.10	0.10	2.00
Fish meal	1.50	1.96	2.00
Slurry	0	5.00	10.00
Total	100	100	100
Calculated Analysis			
Crude protein (%)	17.97	17.39	17.08

Crude Fiber (%)	10.17	9.75	9.29
Digestible Energy (Kcal/kg)	2568	2477	2438

T1 - Treatment 1 shows 0% Biogas slurry inclusion, T2 - Treatment 2 shows 5% Biogas slurry inclusion, T3 - Treatment 3 shows 10% Biogas slurry inclusion

Table 1c. Proximate Composition of Experimental Diet (%)

DIETS			
PARAMETERS	T1	T2	T3
Crude protein (%)	17.97	17.39	17.08
Crude Fiber (%)	10.17	9.75	9.29
Ether Extract (%)	4.38	4.76	4.96
Digestible Energy (Kcal/kg)	2568	2477	2438
Dry matter (%)	96.73	95.91	96.08
Nitrogen free extract (NFE)	56.78	57.61	58.83

T1 - Treatment 1, T2 - Treatment 2, T3 - Treatment 3

Table 2. Faecal Microflora content based on Experimental Diet (%)

DIETS						
PARAMETERS (x10 ⁵)	G1	G2	G3	MEAN ± SD	F	P-VALUE
WEEK 5 CFU/G	29	93	33	1.90 ± 0.876	0.594	0.578
	146	72	12			
	73	77	107			
	84					
WEEK 10 CFU/G	3	15	56	1.90 ± 0.876	0.047	0.954
	58	13	3			
	11	25	41			
	12					

G1 – Control group, G2 – 5% inclusion rate, G3 – 10% inclusion rate, F – ANOVA Variance.

4. Conclusion

It could be concluded that (biogas slurry) dried poultry dropping could be included up to 10% in weaner rabbits diet without adversely affecting the gut coliform content of the animals..

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